

1 **Traditional rye varieties exhibit drought tolerance traits but maintain lower yields than**
2 **modern varieties under drought stress**

3 Marcela Hlaváčová^{1,2*}, Karel Klem^{2,3}, Jaromír Pytela⁴, Otmar Urban³, Natálie Pernicová³, Jan
4 Balek^{1,2}, Daniela Semerádová^{1,2}, Milan Fischer^{1,2,5}, Reimund P. Rötter⁶, Mercy Appiah⁶, Petr
5 Hlavinka^{1,2}, Vladimíra Horáková⁷, Petr Škarpa⁸ and Miroslav Trnka^{1,2}

6 ¹ Department of Climate Change Impacts on Agroecosystems, Global Change Research
7 Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Bělidla 986/4a, Brno, 60300, Czech Republic

8 ² Department of Agrosystems and Bioclimatology, Faculty of AgriSciences, Mendel
9 University in Brno, Zemědělská 1665/1, Brno, 61300, Czech Republic

10 ³ Laboratory of Ecological Plant Physiology, Global Change Research Institute of the Czech
11 Academy of Sciences, Bělidla 986/4a, Brno, 60300, Czech Republic

12 ⁴ Plant Phenotyping and Biotechnology Platform, Photon Systems Instruments, Průmyslová
13 470, Drásov, 66424, Czech Republic

14 ⁵ Department of Matters and Energy Fluxes, Global Change Research Institute of the Czech
15 Academy of Sciences, Bělidla 986/4a, Brno, 60300, Czech Republic

16 ⁶ Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, Department of Crop Sciences, Tropical Plant Production
17 and Agricultural Systems Modelling, Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Wilhelmsplatz 1,
18 Göttingen, 37073, Germany

19 ⁷ Plant Production Section, National Plant Variety Office, Department of Utility Value
20 Testing, Central Institute for Supervising and Testing in Agriculture, Hroznová 63/2, Brno,
21 60300, Czech Republic

22 ⁸ Department of Agrochemistry, Soil Science, Microbiology and Plant Nutrition, Faculty of
23 AgriSciences, Mendel University in Brno, Zemědělská 1665/1, Brno, 61300, Czech Republic

24 ***Corresponding author e-mail:** hlavacova.m@czechglobe.cz;

25 **Contributing authors:** hlavacova.m@czechglobe.cz, [https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3585-](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3585-8499)

26 [8499; klem.k@czechglobe.cz](mailto:klem.k@czechglobe.cz), <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6105-0429>; pytela@psi.cz;

27 urban.o@czechglobe.cz, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1716-8876>;

28 pernicova.n@czechglobe.cz, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0418-7813>; balek.j@czechglobe.cz,

29 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2753-3777>; semeradova.d@czechglobe.cz,

30 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2699-7924>; fischer.m@czechglobe.cz, [https://orcid.org/0000-](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7841-9317)

31 [0002-7841-9317](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7841-9317); reimund.roetter@uni-goettingen.de, [https://orcid.org/0000-](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3804-9964)

32 [9964](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3804-9964); mercy.appiah@uni-goettingen.de, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3953-6350>;

33 hlavinka.p@czechglobe.cz, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5604-5502>;

34 vladimira.horakova@ukzuz.cz; petr.skarpa@mendelu.cz, [https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3189-](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3189-1726)

35 [1726](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3189-1726); trnka.m@czechglobe.cz, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4727-8379>

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ABSTRACT

38 Compared with other cereals, rye (*Secale cereale* L.) has traits that contribute to superior

39 drought tolerance, thus making it a suitable alternative under intensifying droughts related to

40 climate change. The distributions of these traits across a range of varieties and their

41 relationships with yield potential have yet to be fully elucidated. Therefore, the sensitivity of

42 20 varieties, which differ in origin and age, to drought stress between the end of stem

43 elongation/early booting and the beginning of grain filling was analyzed. Potted plants were

44 exposed to drought on an automated phenotyping platform, enabling accurate simulation of

45 water loss for all varieties. A decrease in soil moisture was ensured up to 30% of the soil

46 water capacity, followed by rewetting. Although traditional varieties exhibited greater

47 stability of key yield components under drought stress, modern varieties achieved higher

48 absolute yields under both drought and well-watered conditions. Therefore, traditional
49 varieties cannot replace modern varieties but remain valuable donors of drought resistance
50 traits.

51 **Keywords:** drought stress, phenotyping platform, *Secale cereale* L., yield components

52

53

1 INTRODUCTION

54 Drought is the primary abiotic stress factor that limits cereal production worldwide
55 (Stewart and Lal 2018; Lesk et al. 2016). Based on both 2024 data and the 2020–2024 mean,
56 rye ranks ninth in terms of global production and fifth within the EU-27 (FAOSTAT
57 Database, <http://www.fao.org/faostat/>). Rye is primarily cultivated in Eastern, Central, and
58 Northern Europe (especially in Germany and Poland), as well as Canada, Turkey, Australia,
59 Argentina, and other countries stretching within main rye cultivation areas (i.e., northern
60 latitudes in the range of 30–65° and southern latitudes in the range of 30–50°, as presented by
61 Leff et al. (2004). A high proportion of total produced rye grains – approximately 50–75% –
62 are used for bread baking, mostly in European countries that are traditional producers of rye
63 (Geiger and Miedaner 2009). The rye produced in these regions complements the wheat diet
64 (Hackauf et al. 2022).

65 Rye (*Secale cereale* L.) is a type of crop that can tolerate a wide range of adverse
66 environmental conditions, including poor soils with low nutrient availability, cooler climates,
67 and dry sites (Colombo 2022; Ghafoor et al. 2024). The drought resilience of rye is largely
68 attributed to its deep and extensive root system, as evidenced by traits such as increased root
69 length density, lateral root branching, and enhanced biomass allocation under stress (Gordon-
70 Werner and Dörffling 1988). Among small-grain cereals, rye has the highest overwintering
71 rate and the strongest resilience to drought stress, making it suitable for cultivation even under

72 conditions that are not favorable for the cultivation of any other cereal crop (Geiger and
73 Miedaner 2009). Moreover, modern hybrid rye varieties have relatively high yield potentials,
74 making them competitive with wheat even in fertile soils (Geiger and Miedaner 2009). Rye
75 also has the fastest spring growth among winter cereals, even under water-limited conditions,
76 thereby preventing soil erosion (Geiger and Miedaner 2009; Ghaafor et al. 2024). Due to
77 these features, rye holds promise for sustainable grain production in the face of climate
78 change (Hackauf et al. 2022).

79 While current cereal breeding methods primarily focus on high and stable yields (Geiger
80 and Miedaner 2009), traditional landraces are selected for region-specific environmental
81 stress tolerance (Colombo et al. 2022). This selection process contributes to yield stability
82 (Tesemma et al. 1998) and enhanced resilience to both biotic and abiotic stresses (Newton et
83 al. 2010; Pinheiro de Carvalho et al. 2007; Rossi et al. 2022). In contrast, modern hybrid
84 varieties often lack competitiveness under such adverse conditions (Giupponi et al. 2021).
85 Therefore, developing hybrid rye varieties with stable yields across diverse environmental
86 conditions (Haffke et al. 2015) and enhancing the competitiveness of rye under current
87 agricultural systems (Shawon et al. 2024) are key breeding objectives in the context of
88 climate change. Despite the recognized drought tolerance of rye, little is known about how
89 traditional and modern ryes differ in terms of their tolerance mechanisms, the specific traits
90 underlying this resilience, and how these factors are related to yield performance under both
91 water-sufficient and drought conditions.

92 Therefore, it is essential to evaluate rye varieties for drought tolerance, as rye is a
93 promising cereal crop that can contribute to sustainable cereal production in the context of
94 climate change. Given that drought stress is the primary abiotic factor causing cereal yield
95 losses worldwide, it is crucial to understand the responses of different rye varieties. Therefore,
96 twenty winter rye varieties from various rye-growing regions were examined to determine

97 their tolerance to drought stress during critical growth stages from the end of stem elongation
98 to the beginning of grain filling. The main objectives of this study were as follows: (i) to
99 assess differences in yield formation and physiological parameters between traditional and
100 modern winter rye varieties in response to drought, and (ii) to determine whether traditional
101 rye varieties are more productive than modern varieties under drought conditions. This study
102 aimed to test the following hypotheses: (1) traditional varieties are more productive under
103 drought stress conditions, and (2) modern rye varieties are more productive when there is a
104 sufficient water supply.

105 **2 MATERIALS AND METHODS**

106 **2.1 Plant and soil material**

107 Twenty winter rye varieties (*Secale cereale* L.), including both traditional and modern
108 varieties, were selected from countries spanning a wide range of latitudes within the rye belt
109 (see Supplementary Table S1 and section 2.6.). These varieties were sown on 22 October
110 2018 into 3-L truncated cone plastic pots (height: 20.5 cm, lower base width: 11.5 cm, upper
111 base width: 15.7 cm). The seeds of rye varieties were provided free of charge by the plant
112 genebank GRIN Czech (<https://grinczech.vurv.cz/gringlobal/>), except for those of the
113 unavailable varieties KWS Binntto, KWS Vinetto, SU Cossani, SU Performer, and Inspector.
114 These varieties were provided free of charge by the Central Institute for Supervising and
115 Testing in Agriculture (Brno, Czech Republic).

116 The pots were filled with topsoil (0–30 cm) from the Polkovice experimental site (199 m
117 a.s.l.; Czech Republic). The soil is classified as Luvic Chernozem with loess as a mother
118 substrate and a silty clay texture (70% loam, 21% clay, 9% sand). The soil properties were as
119 follows: The pH (CaCl₂) was 7.16; the N_{tot} was 0.23%; the C_{tot} was 2.53%; and the Mehlich
120 III-extractable Ca, K, Mg, and P contents were 5701, 427, 247, and 84 mg kg⁻¹, respectively.

121 Two seeds were sown in each pot, but only one plant was retained at the beginning of the
122 vegetative season in order to ensure sufficient space for optimal growth. The pots were placed
123 on a concrete floor in a vegetation hall at Mendel University in Brno (235 m a.s.l.;
124 49°12'36.62892" N, 16°36'48.64716" E). The hall had wire netting instead of walls and a
125 roof, allowing exposure to ambient weather conditions. Throughout the vegetation period, the
126 plants were regularly irrigated to prevent drought stress (87 mm in total per vegetation
127 season) and were fertilized and treated for insect pests and fungal diseases using
128 recommended products (see Supplementary Table S2).

129 2.2 Experimental phase

130 At the beginning of the experimental phase, the plants were transported from the
131 vegetation hall to the PlantScreen™ Modular System phenotyping platform (Photon Systems
132 Instruments, Ltd., Drásov, Czech Republic; 265 m a.s.l.; 49°20'14.9" N, 16°28'34.1" E). The
133 experimental phase commenced at the end of stem elongation (DC 37–41 according to
134 Zadoks decimal codes; Zadoks 1974). Prior to the experimental phase, the plants were
135 acclimated for two days in the greenhouse to adapt to the microclimate. Subsequently, all the
136 plants were irrigated to the same level of 70% soil water capacity (SWC) (day 0 –
137 preexperimental stage).

138 The plants were then divided into two treatment groups ($n \geq 4$ per treatment per variety):
139 (1) control plants were irrigated to maintain 70% SWC throughout the experimental phase,
140 while (2) drought-stressed plants were left to dry naturally, with daily irrigation to match the
141 second wettest pot in this treatment. The soil moisture levels were monitored daily using
142 automated weighing and irrigation on the phenotypic platform. When the driest pot in the
143 drought-stressed treatment reached 30% SWC (corresponding to the double value of the
144 permanent wilting point – 15% SWC – of the soil used on the 29th day of the experimental

145 phase), the irrigation of these plants was resumed to match the control treatment (70% SWC)
146 and to allow for their recovery (starting on the 31st day of the experimental phase). Owing to
147 the limited capacity of the phenotyping platform, the control treatment of two randomly
148 selected rye varieties—one traditional variety (Musketeer) and one modern variety (Wrens-
149 5)—was decreased by one plant to 4 repetitions.

150 On the 30th day of the experimental phase, the *in vivo* contents of total chlorophyll (Chl *a*
151 + *b*) in flag leaves were measured using a factory-calibrated Dualex 4 Flav device (Force A,
152 Orsay, France) to assess the leaf senescence rates of both drought-stressed and control plants.
153 The experimental phase was terminated when the mean SWC of the drought-stressed plants
154 equaled that of the control plants (on the 36th day of the experimental phase, corresponding to
155 the beginning of grain filling, DC 71–73; Fig. 1). The plants were then returned to the
156 vegetation hall on the 37th day and cultivated until manual harvest at full ripening (DC 92).
157 Air temperature was recorded at 2 m above ground level in the vegetation hall and above the
158 plant canopy in the PSI Drásov greenhouse. Global radiation and photosynthetically active
159 radiation were measured in the vegetation hall and in the greenhouse of Drásov, respectively.
160 Precipitation during plant cultivation in the vegetation hall was recorded in the nearby
161 arboretum of Mendel University in Brno. Relative air humidity was also measured in Drásov
162 (see Supplementary Fig. S1, S2).

164 **Fig. 1 a** Soil water capacity (SWC; %) of the pots during the experiment from 7 May 2019
165 (day 0) to 12 June 2019 (day 36). On day 0, both drought-stressed and control plants were
166 irrigated to the same level of 70% SWC. The SWC of the drought-stressed plants was
167 subsequently maintained at the level of the second wettest pot within this group. When the
168 driest pot among the drought-stressed plants reached 30% SWC (double the value of the
169 wilting point of 15%) on day 29, reirrigation of the drought-stressed plants started on day 31,
170 restoring the SWC to 70% by day 36. On this day, the mean SWC of the drought-stressed
171 plants matched that of the appropriate control plants. On day 37, all the plants were
172 transported to the vegetation hall. **b** Illustrative photo of the phenotyping platform
173 (PlantScreenTM Modular System) used for the experimental phase

174 **2.3 Assessment of yield traits**

175 The harvested aboveground biomass was dried for 12 h at 105 °C in an automatic drying
176 oven. The aboveground biomass per plant (AB; g) and the combined weight of straw and
177 leaves without spikes (SLW) were subsequently recorded. The spikes were separated, and the
178 grains were manually rolled out to determine yield formation parameters, including the grain
179 number per spike (GN; pcs), grain weight per spike (GW; g), thousand-grain weight (TGW;
180 g; calculated from measured GW and GN), and harvest index (HI; unitless).

181 **2.4 Isotopic analyses**

182 After the assessment of yield formation parameters, the grain samples were analyzed at
183 the Laboratory of Ecological Plant Physiology of the Global Change Research Institute of the
184 Czech Academy of Sciences (Brno, Czech Republic) for stable isotope discrimination ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$
185 and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$).

186 Prior to analysis, the grain samples were homogenized using a Retsch MM400 ball mill
187 (Retsch, Haan, Germany). Approximately 1.5 mg of the homogenized material was placed

188 into tin capsules (Elementar Analysensysteme, Langenselbold, Germany) for isotopic
189 analysis. Carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$; $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$) and nitrogen ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$; $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$) isotope ratios were determined
190 using a varioPYRO cube elemental analyzer (Elementar Analysensysteme, Langenselbold,
191 Germany) coupled to an IsoPrime100 continuous-flow isotope ratio mass spectrometer
192 (Isoprime, Manchester, UK). The elemental analyzer was operated in combustion mode at
193 960 °C.

194 The instrument stability and linearity across the expected ion current range obtained from
195 the test samples were verified before each analytical session. The measurement accuracy,
196 which was assessed through internal reference material (homogenized rye grain powder),
197 presented standard deviations of $< 0.05\text{‰}$ for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $< 0.15\text{‰}$ for $\delta^{15}\text{N}$. The isotopic system
198 was calibrated using a two-point calibration curve based on certified standard reference
199 materials from the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) and the United States
200 Geological Survey (USGS): IAEA-600 (caffeine), USGS-24 (graphite), and USGS-32
201 (potassium nitrate).

202 The resulting $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values are expressed in parts per thousand (‰) relative to the
203 Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite (VPDB) and Atmospheric N_2 (AIR) standards, respectively. These
204 values were calculated using the standard formula, as follows:

$$205 \quad \delta^n X = \left(\frac{R_{\text{sample}}}{R_{\text{standard}} - 1} \right) \times 1000 \quad (1)$$

206 where R represents the ratio of the heavy isotope to the light isotope of element X .

207 **2.5 Drought resistance index (DRI) and aridity index (AI)**

208 The drought resistance index (*DRI*) was calculated based on the formula developed by
209 Lan (1998), as applied by Bennani et al. (2017), for each variety tested (Supplementary Table
210 S1). The equation was as follows:

211
$$DRI = \frac{Y_s \times (\frac{Y_s}{\bar{Y}_p})}{\text{mean } Y_s}, \quad (2)$$

212 where Y_s and \bar{Y}_p represent the grain yield of drought-stressed and control plants, respectively,
213 and the *mean* Y_s is the mean grain yield of all varieties under drought stress.

214 The aridity index (*AI*) was calculated for each country of origin to quantify the degree of
215 climate dryness of the respective growing regions in accordance with the method used by
216 Bannayan et al. (2010) (Supplementary Table S1). First, the Harvested Area and Yield for
217 175 Crops dataset by Monfreda et al. (2008) was used to identify key rye production areas in
218 each country. This dataset was refined using national statistical data, varietal testing records,
219 and national agronomic reports. The final dataset represents the most recent rye production
220 areas for each country (Supplementary Table S3). Precipitation (P) and variables needed for
221 calculations of potential evapotranspiration (PET) were retrieved from the ERA-5 Land
222 database (Muñoz Sabater 2019). PET was subsequently estimated using the FAO-56 Penman-
223 Monteith method (Allen et al. 1998). These values were averaged across the established rye
224 production areas for each country, covering the mean period from sowing to harvest (Sacks et
225 al. 2010) over the climatic normal period 1991–2020. The *AI* was then calculated as the ratio
226 of P/PET following UNEP (1992), and the mean *AI* for 1991–2020 was determined for each
227 location of each country (Supplementary Table S1, S3).

228 **2.6 Data processing and statistical analyses**

229 The Shapiro–Wilk normality test and Brown–Forsythe homogeneity of variance test were
230 performed on all datasets using SigmaPlot 14.5 (Systat Software Inc., San Jose, California,
231 USA; www.systat.com). If the data did not pass the Shapiro–Wilk normality test, Box–Cox
232 transformation was applied using Statistica 14.0.0.15 software (TIBCO Software Inc., Palo
233 Alto, California, USA; www.tibco.com) prior to ANOVA. Two-way ANOVA ($n \geq 4$) was
234 performed with the factors variety (V), treatment (T) and their interaction ($V \times T$), followed

235 by Tukey's honest significant difference (*HSD*) test for unequal sample sizes (Spjøtvoll and
236 Stoline 1973, p. 975) for two significance levels ($p = 0.01$ and $p = 0.05$), to identify
237 statistically significant differences between the rye varieties and treatments (control and
238 drought stress) and to examine their interactive effects on grain weight per spike (GW), grain
239 number per spike (GN), thousand-grain weight (TGW), harvest index (HI), straw and leaves
240 weight (SLW), aboveground biomass per plant (AB), chlorophyll index (CI_F), and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and
241 $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values in grains. These analyses were performed using Statistica 14.0.0.15 software.

242 Rye varieties were classified into two groups according to their registration year (RY) in
243 the GRIN Czech genebank or the National Varietal List of their respective country of origin
244 (see Supplementary Table S1). Based on the classification approach of Lan et al. (2022), rye
245 varieties registered between 1953 and 1990 were categorized as traditional (old), whereas
246 those registered between 1991 and 2018 were considered modern.

247 Paired *t* tests were performed via Origin software (OriginLab Corporation, Northampton,
248 USA; <https://www.originlab.com/>) to identify whether the drought stress effects were
249 statistically significant within traditional ($n = 29$ in the control group and $n = 30$ in the
250 drought stress treatments) and modern ($n = 69$ in the control group and $n = 70$ in the drought
251 stress treatments) variety groups (at two significance levels: $p = 0.05$ and $p = 0.01$).

252 The relative changes in the drought stress treatments compared with the control treatments
253 (*RCC*) for each of these experimental traits were calculated using the following equation:

$$254 \quad RCC = \frac{AVG_{c-D}}{AVG_c} \times 100\%, \quad (3)$$

255 where *AVG_c* is an arithmetic mean of a specific trait under the control treatment and *D* is a
256 corresponding value under the drought stress treatment for a given variety and replication.

257 Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed for RCC, AI, DRI, RY, and grain
258 weight per spike under well-watered conditions (YieldPot) to compare yield potential among
259 varieties. A biplot of the PCA results was generated using CANOCO 5 software (Šmilauer
260 and Lepš 2014). A polar heatmap with cluster analysis for RCC, AI, DRI, RY, and YieldPot
261 and correlation analysis (Pearson's correlation coefficient matrix; $p = 0.05$) for the same
262 datasets were generated via Origin software (OriginLab Corporation, Northampton, USA).

263

3 RESULTS

264 3.1 Chlorophyll indices, yield traits, and ^{15}N and ^{13}C isotope discrimination in grains

265 Drought-induced leaf senescence was assessed by measuring chlorophyll indices (CI_F) at
266 the end of drought stress treatment in flag leaves of control and drought-stressed plants (Fig.
267 2). Both traditional and modern varieties presented similar drought-induced decreases in the
268 mean CI_F (-25.6% and -25.9%, respectively). However, generally, the more modern the
269 variety was, the greater the CI_F was under well-watered conditions, which indicates the
270 higher productivity of modern varieties under optimal moisture conditions. This trend was
271 also observed for the above-ground biomass per plant (AB) and harvest index (HI) results.

272

273 **Fig. 2** Left bar charts: Mean values (columns) and standard errors of the means (error bars)
 274 for the chlorophyll index of a flag leaf, ^{15}N isotope discrimination in grains ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$), and ^{13}C
 275 isotope discrimination in grains ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) under control and drought stress treatments for
 276 individual winter rye varieties. The varieties are divided into traditional and modern varieties
 277 and by country of origin (see Supplementary Table S1 for country codes and full variety
 278 names). Statistically significant differences ($n \geq 4$) among the control and drought stress
 279 (stressed) treatments within individual rye varieties according to two-way ANOVA with
 280 Tukey's *HSD* test are denoted with * and ** symbols at significance levels of $p = 0.05$ and p

281 = 0.01, respectively, if any differences are observed, and the effects of factor variety (V),
282 treatment (T) and their interactive effects ($V \times T$) are also shown. The Tukey *HSD* test results
283 (letters) for $p = 0.05$ are presented in a separate Supplementary Table S4. The blue lines
284 represent the total mean values of the control treatments, and the dark orange lines represent
285 the total mean values of the drought stress treatments. Right boxplots: Boxplot graphs ($n \geq$
286 29) show the mean values ± 1 standard error of the mean (boxes), mean values $\pm 95\%$
287 confidence interval (error bars), medians (horizontal lines within boxes), and mean values
288 (squares within boxes) for the same traits presented in the bar charts. The * symbols and **
289 symbols denote statistically significant differences between the control and drought stress
290 (stressed) treatments within traditional and modern varieties, respectively, according to paired
291 *t* tests at significance levels of $p = 0.05$ and $p = 0.01$, respectively; *n.s.* denotes a statistically
292 insignificant difference. The white arrows with numerical values represent the mean relative
293 change in drought stress compared with the control treatment (RCC) for a specific trait within
294 traditional and modern varieties (a downward/upward arrow indicates a decline/increase in the
295 RCC, respectively)

296

297 In contrast to the *CI_F*, drought-stressed plants of traditional varieties presented higher HI
298 values (Fig. 3) than plants under the control treatment, with a mean relative increase of
299 +15.7%. Therefore, this trait was the most stable in traditional varieties, as the mean spikes
300 under drought stress presented a greater grain number per spike (GN; a mean drought-induced
301 increase of +14.9%) while maintaining their weights (GW; mean drought-induced decline of -
302 8.4%). Thus, these plants maintained or exceeded their varietal mean in thousand-grain
303 weights (TGW; Fig. 4). However, in general, traditional varieties presented lower GW, GN,
304 HI, and AB values than modern varieties for under both well-watered and drought-stressed
305 conditions. In contrast to traditional varieties, GW was the second most severely affected trait

306 in modern varieties after AB, with a mean drought-induced reduction in the GW of -31.8%. In
 307 modern varieties, the mean drought-induced decrease in the HI was -11.5%, making it the
 308 second least affected trait after ¹³C isotopic discrimination in grains. The most pronounced
 309 drought-induced decreases in the HI were observed in the modern varieties Elbon Gator 17 (-
 310 31.2%) and Conduct (-29.4%), both of which also presented severe decreases in other yield
 311 parameters and the CI_F (the mean decreases in all the parameters were -32.3% and -33.5%,
 312 respectively), indicating the drought sensitivity of these varieties.

313
 314 **Fig. 3** Left bar charts: Mean values (columns) and standard errors of the means (error bars)
 315 for the harvest index, straw and leaf weights, and aboveground biomass per plant under the

316 control and drought stress treatments for individual winter rye varieties. The varieties are
317 divided into traditional and modern varieties and by country of origin (see Supplementary
318 Table S1 for country codes and full variety names). Statistically significant differences ($n \geq 4$)
319 among the control and drought stress (stressed) treatments within individual rye varieties
320 according to two-way ANOVA with Tukey's *HSD* test are denoted with * and ** symbols at
321 significance levels of $p = 0.05$ and $p = 0.01$, respectively, if any differences are observed, and
322 the effects of factor variety (V), treatment (T) and their interactive effects ($V \times T$) are also
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330 between the control and drought stress (stressed) treatments within traditional and modern
331 varieties, respectively, according to paired *t* tests at significance levels of $p = 0.05$ and $p =$
332 0.01 , respectively; *n.s.* denotes a statistically insignificant difference. The white arrows with
333 numerical values represent the mean relative change in drought stress compared with the
334 control treatment (RCC) for a specific trait within traditional and modern varieties (a
335 downward/upward arrow indicates a decline/increase in the RCC, respectively)

336

337 **Fig. 4** Left bar charts: Mean values (columns) and standard errors of the means (error bars)
 338 for grain weight per spike, grain number per spike, and thousand-grain weight under control
 339 and drought stress treatments for individual winter rye varieties. The varieties are divided into
 340 traditional and modern varieties and divided based on country of origin (see Supplementary
 341 Table S1 for country codes and full variety names). Statistically significant differences ($n \geq 4$)
 342 among the control and drought stress (stressed) treatments within individual rye varieties
 343 according to two-way ANOVA with Tukey's *HSD* test are denoted with * and ** symbols at
 344 significance levels of $p = 0.05$ and $p = 0.01$, respectively, if any differences are observed, and

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352 the bar charts. The * symbols and ** symbols denote statistically significant differences
353 between the control and drought stress treatments within traditional and modern varieties,
354 respectively, according to paired *t* tests at significance levels of $p = 0.05$ and $p = 0.01$,
355 respectively; *n.s.* denotes a statistically insignificant difference. The white arrows with
356 numerical values represent the mean relative change in drought stress compared with the
357 control treatment (RCC) for a specific trait within traditional and modern varieties (a
358 downward/upward arrow indicates a decline/increase in the RCC, respectively)

359

360 AB (Fig. 3) was the most drought-sensitive trait in 12 out of the 20 rye varieties tested
361 herein. The mean drought-induced declines in AB were -34.9% and -36.3% in traditional and
362 modern varieties, respectively. The effect of drought was statistically significant for the
363 Musketeer ($p = 0.014$) and Prima ($p < 0.001$) traditional varieties as well as the Naico ($p =$
364 0.001), KWS Binntto ($p = 0.005$), KWS Vinetto ($p = 0.003$), SU Performer ($p = 0.003$),
365 Conduct ($p = 0.008$), and Matador ($p = 0.003$) modern varieties. The least severe drought-
366 induced reductions in AB were observed in Stupicke S II (-1.41%) and Dukato (-3.6%).
367 Stupicke S II, the oldest variety in this study, also presented the highest stability in the GN,
368 GW, and HI, with drought-induced increases of +74.7%, +51.1%, and +44.5%, respectively.
369 Thus, Stupicke S II maintained a TGW slightly above the varietal mean under drought stress.

370 Dukato showed similar trends, with the highest stability observed in the GW (+16.4%), HI
371 (+13.2%), TGW (+9.0%), and GN (+7.6%). In contrast, the greatest decreases in the AB were
372 observed in the traditional variety Prima (-58.8%) and in the modern variety Matador (-
373 50.6%), with corresponding reductions in the GW (-33.6% and -37.6%, respectively). In
374 Matador, drought stress also caused an accelerated decrease in the CI_F (-35.8%) and the GN.

375 Drought stress resulted in consistent declines in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values across both traditional and
376 modern varieties, with mean drought-induced decreases of -4.7% in traditional varieties and -
377 5.1% in modern varieties (Fig. 2). In contrast to the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values, the mean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (Fig. 2)
378 in the control treatment were slightly greater in the traditional varieties than in the modern
379 varieties, indicating higher water use efficiency under well-watered conditions. On average,
380 drought caused an increase in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of -19.4% in traditional varieties and -20.0% in
381 modern varieties.

382 Two-way ANOVA confirmed the statistically significant effects of both variety and
383 treatment across all tested traits; however, a significant interactive effect was detected only
384 for the AB ($p = 0.002$). The results of Tukey's post hoc tests, which examined homogeneous
385 groups among individual treatments across specific rye varieties separately for each tested
386 trait, are summarized in Supplementary Table S4, where different letters denote statistically
387 significant differences at a significance level of $p = 0.05$.

388 **3.2 Principal component analysis of the response to drought**

389 Principal component analysis (PCA) explained 22.9% of the overall variability (PC1
390 14.4% and PC2 8.5%) (Fig. 5). The relative values of yield parameters (relative level under
391 drought conditions (RCC)) were negatively associated with the year of registration (RY),
392 indicating that older varieties maintained a higher relative GW under drought stress. In
393 contrast, the reductions in the AB and GN were more closely related to the DRI, which

394 characterizes the aridity of the breeding environment. Varieties from more arid conditions
 395 (i.e., higher DRIs) presented higher relative AB and GN values under drought stress. The AI
 396 was most strongly associated with the relative SLW. The PCA biplot further revealed that
 397 changes in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values were positively associated with the relative values of yield parameters
 398 (especially GW and HI), suggesting its potential as an indicator of yield response. The
 399 drought-induced changes in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ were positively associated with the relative TGW and CI_F
 400 values, indicating its relevance to grain formation during ripening and senescence.

401 PCA also revealed a clear separation between older traditional and modern rye varieties,
 402 with traditional varieties clustering toward a higher relative GW under drought stress. The
 403 exception was the Montalegre variety, which, despite its older origin, exhibited greater
 404 sensitivity to drought stress. Among modern varieties, Choigue and Dukato presented greater
 405 drought tolerance but also a lower absolute GW under irrigated control conditions, similar to
 406 old, traditional varieties.

408 **Fig. 5** Principal component analysis (PCA) of relative changes induced by drought stress
409 compared with the control treatments for grain weight per spike (GW), grain number per
410 spike (GN), straw and leaf weight (SLW), thousand-grain weight (TGW), harvest index (HI),
411 aboveground biomass (AB), chlorophyll index (CI_F), isotopic composition ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$),
412 and year of variety registration (RY). The RY data were obtained from the GRIN Czech
413 genebank (<https://grinczech.vurv.cz/gringlobal/>) or, when unavailable, from the National
414 Varietal List of a specific country of variety origin (for SU Performer, KWS Binntto, SU
415 Cossani and KWS Vinetto). Additionally, the aridity index (AI) and drought resistance index
416 (DRI) were included in the analysis. The modern rye varieties are indicated in bold, whereas
417 the traditional varieties are presented in plain text

418 **3.3 Polar heatmap with cluster analysis of the response to drought**

419 The polar heatmap (Fig. 6) clustered varieties according to the relative drought response
420 (RCC) and indicators of origin (AI indices), age (RY), and yield potential (absolute grain
421 weight per spike presented as YieldPot for comparisons of yield potentials of the varieties and
422 DRI indices). Within the polar heatmap, three main clusters were identified. The red cluster
423 includes varieties that are older in origin or have lower yield potential, but their responses to
424 drought stress are considerably heterogenous. Some varieties, such as Stupicke S II, Choigue,
425 Caudar, and Cinquecento, maintained high relative yields under drought stress, whereas
426 others, such as Musketeer, Prima, and Wrens-5, presented lower relative yields. This cluster
427 was characterized by a stable HI and a partially stable TGW under drought conditions, with
428 relative $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values hovering around the mean.

429 The blue cluster included mostly modern rye varieties that presented rather negative
430 responses of CI_F, TGW, and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ to drought. Additionally, the GN, GW, and HI were below
431 average, whereas SLW values were above average. Some varieties, particularly KWS Binntto,
432 KWS Vinetto, SU Cossani, and Dankowskie Rubin, presented relatively high $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values.

433 Despite their relatively low yield parameters under drought stress, these varieties presented
434 some of the highest absolute yields under well-watered conditions, particularly KWS Binntto.
435 Additionally, under drought conditions, their absolute yields were among the highest.

436 The green cluster included modern varieties (Naico, Conduct, and SU Performer) with
437 positive drought responses. These varieties presented above-average relative values for CI_F,
438 TGW, and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ under drought stress. These findings suggested that the physiological
439 responses to drought in the green cluster differ from that of the blue cluster, particularly in
440 terms of senescence induction.

441 Overall, the clustering analysis highlighted distinct drought response strategies among rye
442 varieties, with older varieties generally exhibiting greater stability in terms of relative yield
443 parameters and some modern varieties showing adaptation via improved water use efficiency
444 ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) or biomass maintenance ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$).

445

446 **Fig. 6** Polar heatmap with cluster analysis for relative changes in the drought stress treatments
447 compared with the control treatments for grain weight per spike (GW), grain number per
448 spike (GN), straw and leaf weight (SLW), thousand-grain weight (TGW), harvest index (HI),
449 aboveground biomass (AB), chlorophyll index (CI_F), isotopes $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (d13C) and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (d15N),
450 and year of variety seed registration (RY) to the plant gene bank of GRIN Czech
451 (<https://grinczech.vurv.cz/gringlobal/>) or year of registration to the National Varietal List of a
452 specific country of a variety origin in the case of no data availability in the GRIN Czech
453 database (SU Performer, KWS Binntto, SU Cossani and KWS Vinetto), aridity index (AI),
454 and drought resistance index (DRI). The yield performance of a variety is expressed as grain
455 weight per spike in the control treatments as YieldPot parameters in the heatmap

456

457 **3.4 Correlation analysis of the response to drought**

458 The results of the correlation analysis (Fig. 7) revealed strong associations among
459 production parameters, especially between the GW, GN, HI, and AB. These findings indicate
460 that the yield response to drought is closely related to reduction in the AB. Specifically, the
461 decrease in the AB due to drought was closely related to the decreases in the GW and GN,
462 highlighting that yield losses were mainly associated with a lower GN. In contrast, the TGW
463 was only weakly correlated with the AB, and the correlation of the TGW with the GW was
464 weaker than the correlation of the GN with the GW. These findings indicate that some
465 varieties were able to partially compensate for decreases in the GN by increasing the TGW,
466 particularly those that maintained stable CI_F values under drought stress.

467 Negative correlations were observed between the relative response of yield parameters
468 and yield potential under well-watered conditions. This correlation was particularly strong for
469 GW, GN, and HI, indicating that varieties with greater yield potential were more sensitive to

470 drought, whereas those with lower yield potential presented a more stable response.
 471 Furthermore, the drought-induced decrease in TGW was well indicated by the reduction in
 472 $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, supporting its role as a marker of nitrogen dynamics under drought stress.

473
 474 **Fig. 7** Pearson's correlation coefficient ($p = 0.05$) matrix for relative changes of the drought
 475 stress to the control treatments for grain weight per spike (GW), grain number per spike (GN),
 476 straw and leaves weight (SLW), thousand-grain weight (TGW), harvest index (HI),
 477 aboveground biomass (AB), chlorophyll index (CI_F), isotopes $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (d13C) and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (d15N),
 478 and year of variety seeds registration (RY) to the plant genebank of GRIN Czech
 479 (<https://grinczech.vurv.cz/gringlobal/>) or year of registration to the National Varietal List of a
 480 specific country of a variety origin in the case of no data availability in the GRIN Czech
 481 database (SU Performer, KWS Binntto, SU Cossani and KWS Vinetto), aridity index (AI),
 482 and drought resistance index (DRI), including the absolute value of grain weight per spike in
 483 the control treatments presented as YieldPot for comparisons of yield potentials of the
 484 varieties

4 DISCUSSION

485

486 Rye is particularly susceptible to drought during the period from three weeks before
487 anthesis to a few days after anthesis. This period is when the grain number, which is
488 determined by the number of spikes per square meter and the number of grains per spike, is
489 most strongly affected, leading to significant yield reductions under drought stress (Kottmann
490 et al. 2016). In this study, the drought-sensitive period was extended to include approximately
491 one week before the beginning of the sensitive period and after its end. Drought before
492 anthesis mainly reduces the number of spikes per square meter and the GN, which are crucial
493 yield components set before anthesis, in contrast to the TGW, which is formed later
494 (Kottmann et al. 2016).

495 The findings of this study highlight that drought resistance in rye is associated primarily
496 with the RY. Older varieties generally present a relatively high GW and high values of other
497 production parameters under drought conditions, despite their relatively low yield potential.
498 An analysis of the response of individual traits in resistant varieties revealed that these
499 varieties differ in their yield formation strategies. Some varieties, such as Stupicke S II,
500 Choique, and Caudar, are more resistant to the GN, whereas others are more resistant to the
501 TGW (Dukato, Wrens-5, Musketeer, Cinquecento, Choique, Caudar). Stupicke S II and
502 Dukato are typical examples of drought tolerance through the GN and TGW, respectively,
503 whereas Choique and Caudar appear to combine both mechanisms.

504 Under drought conditions, rye plants increasingly rely on pre-anthesis carbohydrate
505 reserves for grain filling, which helps mitigate reductions in the GW. This remobilization is
506 crucial for maintaining yield under water-limited conditions (Kottmann et al. 2016). Varieties
507 with lower drought-induced senescence and prolonged green area retention (in this study, e.g.,
508 SU Performer, Caudar, Wrens-5, or Naico) are generally characterized by the lower
509 sensitivity of the TGW to drought. However, the ability to accumulate assimilates before

510 flowering also plays an important role, which also differentiates the relationship between the
511 effects of drought on the CI_F and TGW values. Thus, while RY is the unifying factor in
512 drought resistance, considerable diversity exists in the traits contributing to resistance. Given
513 their lower yield potential, older varieties are better suited as donors of drought resistance
514 traits than as direct replacements for modern rye varieties.

515 The superior drought resistance of older cereal crop varieties compared with modern high-
516 yield varieties is likely due to their superior root architecture, tighter stomatal regulation,
517 stronger osmotic adjustment, and enhanced antioxidant defenses (Licaj et al. 2023, 2024a;
518 Slama et al. 2018). Genetic studies have identified unique alleles in older varieties linked to
519 root traits, emphasizing the role of these alleles in drought resilience (Bacher et al. 2023;
520 Bonfiglioli et al. 2024). Older varieties present deeper roots, greater lateral root length, higher
521 root-to-shoot ratios, and increased xylem vessel adaptations, increasing water uptake under
522 drought (Licaj et al. 2023; Shoaib et al. 2022). In older varieties, tighter stomatal control,
523 reduced stomatal density, and enhanced ABA signaling help conserve water while
524 maintaining gas exchange during drought stress (Licaj et al. 2024b). Compared with modern
525 varieties, some older varieties excel in osmotic adjustment through increased proline and
526 soluble sugar accumulation, increased ROS scavenging, reduced oxidative damage, and
527 improved chlorophyll retention under stress (Slama et al. 2018). Older varieties achieve a
528 better balance between root growth and grain filling, thus buffering against the impact of
529 drought, whereas modern varieties prioritize yield-related traits, such as optimized
530 reproductive biomass, at the expense of vegetative resilience, thus reducing their adaptability
531 under stress (Reynolds et al. 2007; Slama et al. 2018).

532 Stable isotope analysis, particularly for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, provides valuable insights into
533 plant water use efficiency (WUE) and nitrogen metabolism, respectively, under stress
534 conditions, making this analysis a promising tool for selecting drought-resistant crops.

535 Consistent with previous studies on wheat (Pernicová et al. 2023; Rezzouk et al. 2022), barley
536 (Sánchez-Díaz et al. 2002), and triticale (Munjonji and Ayisi 2021), this study revealed
537 relatively high $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values in drought-treated rye varieties, indicating their ability to improve
538 the intrinsic WUE. However, the relationship between $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and WUE is further influenced by
539 environmental factors such as irradiation, soil texture, and irrigation regimes, which may
540 affect the reliability of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ as an indicator under specific conditions (Wang et al. 2022).
541 Additionally, higher carbon isotope discrimination (more negative $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values) is often
542 associated with lower yield potential due to reduced water use in environments where water is
543 not the limiting factor. This is because traits that increase WUE, such as reduced stomatal
544 conductance, can limit carbon assimilation and growth, thereby reducing yield potential under
545 non-drought conditions (Blum 2009).

546 While previous studies have validated $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ as a drought-related proxy in rye, few studies
547 have combined $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ to assess drought-related traits. In particular, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ has been
548 analyzed in grains and flag leaves to evaluate its relationship with WUE and drought
549 adaptability under controlled water regimes, revealing correlations with grain yield under
550 severe drought but inconsistencies across years and tissue types (Kottmann et al. 2014). In
551 durum wheat, integrating $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (WUE) and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (nitrogen use efficiency – NUE)
552 distinguished genotypic drought tolerance, with higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values reflecting water stress
553 adaptation and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values reflecting shifts in nitrogen metabolism and internal nitrogen
554 recycling (Araus et al. 2013; Yousfi et al. 2012). In accordance with these studies, this study
555 revealed lower $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values in the grains of drought-treated plants than in those of well-
556 watered plants.

557 Several mechanisms may contribute to the observed decline in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values under drought
558 stress, all of which are governed by the balance between nitrogen demand and supply.
559 Reduced nitrogen requirements for growth and biomass production in drought-stressed plants

560 lead to increased discrimination against ^{15}N during NO_3^- and particularly NH_4^+ uptake from
561 the soil, resulting in lower $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values in plant tissues (Kalcsits et al. 2014). Additionally,
562 reduced nitrogen demand may lead to less efficient assimilation of inorganic nitrogen and its
563 re-translocation within plants, further decreasing grain $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values under drought stress
564 (Raimanová and Haberle 2010). Furthermore, reduced stomatal conductance in drought-
565 stressed plants may limit the preferential loss of ^{14}N -containing volatilized ammonia and
566 nitrous oxide, thus contributing to the observed decline in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values (Farquhar et al. 1980;
567 Smart and Bloom 2001).

568 **5 CONCLUSION**

569 This study examined the responses of twenty winter rye varieties, which differed in age
570 and originated from various climatic conditions, to drought stress applied during their most
571 sensitive growth stages, including flowering. The hypotheses proposed in this study were
572 largely supported.

573 (1) Compared with traditional varieties, modern rye varieties achieved higher absolute
574 yields under drought conditions. However, modern rye varieties also exhibited greater
575 sensitivity to drought stress, with more pronounced yield reductions relative to their potential.

576 (2) Compared with modern varieties, traditional rye varieties are more resilient to drought,
577 particularly in terms of the stability of specific yield components, such as grain number per
578 spike (GN) and thousand-grain weight (TGW), despite their overall lower yield potential.

579 Correlation analysis revealed that the drought response is closely related to the AB,
580 indicating that high-yielding varieties are more sensitive to drought stress, whereas lower-
581 yielding varieties exhibit a reduced drought response. Additionally, the drought-induced
582 decrease in the TGW was reflected by the reduction in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$.

583 Drought resistance in rye involves the resilience of various yield components. Resistance
584 to the GN was observed among older (traditional) varieties, such as Stupicke S II and
585 Choigue, as well as in the modern variety Caudar. In contrast, resistance to the TGW was
586 observed among the modern varieties Dukato, Wrens-5, and Choigue and in the traditional
587 varieties Musketeer, Cinquecento, and Caudar. While Stupicke S II and Dukato are typical
588 examples of drought tolerance through GN and TGW, respectively, Choigue and Caudar are
589 likely to combine both mechanisms. Moreover, varieties such as SU Performer, Caudar,
590 Wrens-5, and Naico, which presented lower sensitivity of senescence to drought, generally
591 maintained greater TGW stability.

592 In conclusion, while modern varieties tend to be more productive than traditional varieties
593 under both well-watered and drought conditions, older varieties remain valuable as genetic
594 sources for the breeding of drought resistance traits rather than as direct replacements for
595 modern high-yielding rye varieties.

596

597 **SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION**

598 The Supplementary Information provides additional information on the rye varieties used
599 (Supplementary Table S1), applications of fertilizers and treatments for pests and diseases
600 (Supplementary Table S2), input data for the aridity index calculation (Supplementary Table
601 S3), the results of Tukey's *HSD* test of two-way ANOVA presented in Fig. 2, 3 and 4
602 (Supplementary Table S4) and the courses of meteorological variables recorded in the
603 vegetation hall of Mendel University in Brno and in the greenhouse of PSI Drásov
604 (Supplementary Fig. S1, S2).

605

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606

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612

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

613

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

614

ETHICS APPROVAL

615

Not applicable.

616

CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

617

Not applicable.

618

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION

619

Not applicable.

620

DATA AVAILABILITY

621

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within

622

the article and its Supplementary Information.

623

624

625

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

626 The authors contributed to this study in the following ways: Conceptualization – KK and MT;
627 Data curation – MH., KK, OU, NP and MT; Formal analysis – MH, KK, OU, NP, RPR, MA,
628 MF, DS and JB; Investigation – MH, KK, JP, OU, NP and MT; Methodology – KK and MT;
629 Project administration – MH, KK, JP and MT; Resources – JP, PH, VH, DS, JB, MF and PŠ;
630 Supervision – MH, KK and MT; Visualization – MH and KK; Writing – original draft – MH,
631 KK, OU and NP; Writing – review and editing – MH, KK, OU, NP and MT. All the authors
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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Traditional rye varieties exhibit drought tolerance traits but maintain lower yields than modern varieties under drought stress

Marcela Hlaváčová^{1,2*}, Karel Klem^{2,3}, Jaromír Pytela⁴, Otmar Urban³, Natálie Pernicová³, Jan Balek^{1,2}, Daniela Semerádová^{1,2}, Milan Fischer^{1,2,5}, Reimund P. Rötter⁶, Mercy Appiah⁶, Petr Hlavinka^{1,2}, Vladimíra Horáková⁷, Petr Škarpa⁸ and Miroslav Trnka^{1,2}

¹ Department of Climate Change Impacts on Agroecosystems, Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Bělidla 986/4a, Brno, 60300, Czech Republic

² Department of Agrosystems and Bioclimatology, Faculty of AgriSciences, Mendel University in Brno, Zemědělská 1665/1, Brno, 61300, Czech Republic

³ Laboratory of Ecological Plant Physiology, Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Bělidla 986/4a, Brno, 60300, Czech Republic

⁴ Plant Phenotyping and Biotechnology Platform, Photon Systems Instruments, Průmyslová 470, Drásov, 66424, Czech Republic

⁵ Department of Matters and Energy Fluxes, Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Bělidla 986/4a, Brno, 60300, Czech Republic

⁶ Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, Department of Crop Sciences, Tropical Plant Production and Agricultural Systems Modelling, Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Wilhelmsplatz 1, Göttingen, 37073, Germany

⁷ Plant Production Section, National Plant Variety Office, Department of Utility Value Testing, Central Institute for Supervising and Testing in Agriculture, Hroznová 63/2, Brno, 60300, Czech Republic

⁸ Department of Agrochemistry, Soil Science, Microbiology and Plant Nutrition, Faculty of AgriSciences, Mendel University in Brno, Zemědělská 1665/1, Brno, 61300, Czech Republic

***Corresponding author**

Marcela Hlaváčová, Department of Climate Change Impacts on Agroecosystems, Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Bělidla 986/4a, 603 00 Brno, Czech Republic.

E-mail: hlavacova.m@czechglobe.cz

Supplementary Information, containing nine pages, consists of four tables (Supplementary Table S1, S2, S3, and S4) and two figures (Supplementary Fig. S1 and S2).

Supplementary Table S1

List of winter rye varieties tested within the study. Abbreviations of varieties used in the bar charts, countries of origin, years of seed registration to the plant genebank GRIN Czech (<https://grinczech.vurv.cz/gringlobal/>), status of a variety (registered – R or not registered – NR) in the National

List of Varieties, aridity index (AI) and drought resistance index (DRI) of individual varieties are presented

Variety	Abbreviation	Origin ¹	Registration year ³	Registration in the National List of Varieties	AI ⁴	DRI ⁵
Musketeer	MUSK	Canada, CAN	1987	R	1.024	0.754
Prima	PRIM	Canada, CAN	1987	R	1.024	0.539
Stupicke S II	STUP	Czechoslovakia, CSK ^{b2}	1953	NR	1.232	1.302
Cinquecento	CINQ	Italy, ITA	1985	NR	1.686	0.900
Montalegre	MONT	Portugal, PRT	1987	NR	1.902	0.494
Caudar	CAUD	Turkey, TUR	1967	NR	0.664	0.612
Choigue	CHOI	Argentina, ARG	1995	NR	0.641	0.830
Naico	NAIC	Argentina, ARG	1995	NR	0.641	0.552
Elbon Gator 17	ELBO	Australia, AUS	1991	NR	0.219	0.480
Wrens-5	WREN	Australia, AUS	1991	NR	0.219	0.606
KWS Binntto	KWSB	Germany, DEU	2017	R	1.168	0.838
KWS Vinetto	KWSV	Germany, DEU	2018	R	1.168	0.675
SU Cossani	SUCO	Germany, DEU	2014	NR	1.168	0.933
SU Performer	SUPE	Germany, DEU	2013	R	1.168	1.026
Conduct	COND	Germany, DEU	2007	R	1.168	0.368
Dukato	DUKA	Germany, DEU	2013	R	1.168	1.061
Inspector	INSP	Germany, DEU	2016	R	1.168	0.547
Matador	MATA	Germany, DEU	2002	NR	1.168	0.705

Variety	Abbreviation	Origin ¹	Registration year ³	Registration in the National List of Varieties	AI ⁴	DRI ⁵
Dankowskie Amber	DANA	Poland, POL	2014	R	1.111	0.603
Dankowskie Rubin	DANR	Poland, POL	2014	R	1.111	0.766

¹Country of variety origin was abbreviated according to standard ISO 3166: <https://www.iban.com/country-codes>

²No longer a country since 1 January 1993 (the Czech Republic and Slovak Republic emerged).

³Traditional (1953–1990) and modern (1991–2018) varieties based on the seed registration in the plant genebank of the GRIN Czech (<https://grinczech.vurv.cz/gringlobal/>) or year of registration to the National Varietal List of a specific country of a variety origin in the case of no data availability in the GRIN Czech database (SU Performer, KWS Binntto, SU Cossani and KWS Vinetto).

⁴AI – aridity index, $AI = P/PET$ by UNEP (1992), where P is precipitation (mm) and PET (mm) is the potential evapotranspiration, calculated for the time from sowing to harvest of rye (specific for each country) as a mean AI of the years of the last climate normal 1991–2020. The aridity indices were restricted only to areas of real highest rye production for recent years until 2023 in specific countries of various origins and/or based on available literature sources (see Supplemental Table S3 for detailed information).

⁵DRI – Drought resistance index by Lan (1998), as presented in Bennani et al. (2017), $DRI = [Y_s \times (Y_s/Y_p)]/mean Y_s$, where Y_s and Y_p are the grain yields of a variety under stress and the control treatment, respectively, and the $mean Y_s$ is the mean grain yield of all varieties under stress treatment.

Supplementary Table S2

List of application dates of fertilizers and treatments for pests and diseases

Application date	Substance (dose/concentration; type)	Active ingredients
5 April 2019	calcium ammonium nitrate (15.4 kg ha ⁻¹ ; <i>F</i>)	27% N (13.5% N-NO ₃ ⁻ + 13.5% N-NH ₄ ⁺), 7% CaO, 5% MgO
8 April 2019	Boogie _{xpro} (0.3%; <i>FC</i>) ¹	50 g L ⁻¹ bixafen, 100 g L ⁻¹ prothioconazole, 250 g L ⁻¹ spiroxamine
8 April 2019	NURELLE D (0.2%; <i>IC</i>) ¹	500 g L ⁻¹ chlorpyrifos, 50 g L ⁻¹ cypermethrin
15 April 2019	FERTILEADER Vital-954 (0.2%; <i>F</i>)	104 g L ⁻¹ N, 58 g L ⁻¹ P ₂ O ₅ , 46 g L ⁻¹ K ₂ O, 1160 mg Mn, 580 mg B, 580 mg Zn, 232 mg Cu, 232 mg Fe, 116 mg Mo, Seactive® (IPA, glycin betain, amino acids)
30 April 2019	calcium ammonium nitrate (15.4 kg ha ⁻¹ ; <i>F</i>)	27% N (13.5% N-NO ₃ ⁻ + 13.5% N-NH ₄ ⁺), 7% CaO, 5% MgO
30 April 2019	Proteus® 110 OD (0.2%; <i>IC</i>) ¹	100 g L ⁻¹ thiacloprid, 10 g L ⁻¹ deltamethrin
30 April 2019	Boogie _{xpro} (0.3%; <i>FC</i>) ¹	50 g L ⁻¹ bixafen, 100 g L ⁻¹ prothioconazole, 250 g L ⁻¹ spiroxamine
16 May 2019	Proteus® 110 OD (0.2%; <i>IC</i>) ¹	100 g L ⁻¹ thiacloprid, 10 g L ⁻¹ deltamethrin
16 May 2019	Boogie _{xpro} (0.3%; <i>FC</i>) ¹	50 g L ⁻¹ bixafen, 100 g L ⁻¹ prothioconazole, 250 g L ⁻¹ spiroxamine

Note: Abbreviations: *F*, fertilizer; *FC*, fungicide; *IC*, insecticide.

¹Combined treatment at one dose.

Supplementary Table S3

Input data for the aridity index calculation for individual countries of varieties origins

Country	Rye production area for aridity index calculation	Information source	Websites	Years of rye data considered for recent rye production areas establishment	Rye sowing (Julian days) ⁵	Rye harvest (Julian days) ⁵	Mean P (1991–2020) ⁶	Mean PET (1991–2020) ⁷
Canada, CAN	Southwest Manitoba (Manitoba 5)	Statistics Canada	https://www.statcan.gc.ca/en/start	2017–2023	261.5	202.0	470.26	462.18
Czech Republic ¹	Kraj Vysočina	Czech Statistical Office	https://csu.gov.cz/home	2017–2023	274.2	180.3	529.08	386.30
Slovakia ¹	Nitriansky kraj	Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic	https://slovak.statistics.sk	2010–2023	274.0	179.5	497.39	467.61
Italy, ITA	Catanzaro province, Calabria region	The Italian National Institute of Statistics data warehouse	https://esploradati.istat.it/databrowser/#/en/dw	2017–2023	319.0	159.0	621.27	370.36
Portugal, PRT	Norte region	Statistics Portugal	https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_main	2017–2023	274.5	181.5	1022.43	540.98
Turkey, TUR	Niğde province, Anadolu Bölgesi region	Turkish Statistical Institute Database	https://biruni.tuik.gov.tr/medas/?kn=92&locale=en	2017–2023	304.0	212.5	472.96	716.01
Argentina, ARG ²	General Roca departement, Córdoba province	Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries Data	https://datos.magyp.gob.ar/	2012–2021	301.0	153.0	598.83	957.14
Australia, AUS	The Mallee region, Victoria territory	Grains Research & Development Corporation (GRDC), 2018. Cereal Rye Southern Region - GrowNotes.	https://grdc.com.au/resources-and-publications/grownotes/crop-agronomy/cereal-rye-southern-region-grownotes	-	232.5	209.5	310.16	1452.63
		Department of Primary Industries and Regions (PIRSA) ³	https://pir.sa.gov.au/	2021–2023				

Country	Rye production area for aridity index calculation	Information source	Websites	Years of rye data considered for recent rye production areas establishment	Rye sowing (Julian days) ⁵	Rye harvest (Julian days) ⁵	Mean P (1991–2020) ⁶	Mean PET (1991–2020) ⁷
Germany, DEU ⁴	Brandenburg federal state	Uhlmann, F., Kleinhanß, W., 2002. Analyse zur Roggenmarktpolitik: alternative Ausgestaltung oder Abschaffung der Roggenintervention? Bundesforschungsanstalt für Landwirtschaft Institut für Marktanalyse und Agrarhandelspolitik, Braunschweig.	https://literatur.thuenen.de/digbib_extern/zi027477.pdf	1990, 1992, 1995, 2001	274.5	181.5	476.15	410.78
		The database of the Federal Statistical Office	https://www-genesis.destatis.de/datenbank/online/	2017–2023				
Poland, POL	Województwo Wielkopolskie	Statistics Poland	https://dbw.stat.gov.pl/en/baza-danych	2017–2023	274.0	179.5	450.91	409.59

^aAridity index for Czechoslovakia was calculated as a mean aridity index for the Czech Republic (1.383) and Slovakia (1.081).

^bAvailable only up to harvest 2021.

^cCrop and pasture reports.

^dThe agronomical data on rye also include other winter sown cereals since 2004 in Germany and hence, also publication with older data only for rye was used.

^eSowing and harvest dates were taken from SAGE CropCalendar (<https://sage.nelson.wisc.edu/data-and-models/datasets/crop-calendar-dataset/>), as described by Sacks et al. (2010).

^fData from the ERA-5 land database by Muñoz Sabater (2019).

^gCalculated via the FAO-56 Penman–Monteith method by Allen et al. (1998).

Supplementary Table S4

Different letters denote statistically significant differences among means tested by two-way ANOVA with Tukey's *HSD* test ($p = 0.05$, $n \geq 4$) separately for each parameter of grain weight per spike (g; GW), grain number per spike (pcs; GN), thousand-grain weight (g; TGW), harvest index (unitless; HI), straw and leaf weight (g; SLW), aboveground biomass per plant (g; AB), chlorophyll index (Duaex units; CI_F), and ^{15}N (‰; $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) and ^{13}C (‰; $\delta^{13}\text{C}$) isotope discriminations in grains from the control (Control) and drought stress (Stressed) treatments of 20 rye varieties. The level of significance of the factor variety (V), treatment (T), and their interactive effect ($V \times T$) for each experimental trait and the statistically significant differences among drought stress and the appropriate control treatment for individual rye varieties according to two-way ANOVA's Tukey *HSD* test, denoted with * symbols (for $p < 0.05$) and ** symbols (for $p < 0.01$), are presented in Fig. 2, Fig. 3 and Fig. 4

Variety	GW (g)		GN (pcs)		TGW (g)		HI (unitless)		SLW (g)		AB (g)		CI_F (Duaex units)		$\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (‰)		$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰)	
	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed
Musketeer	abcde	abcd	abcdefg	abcdefg	abcdef	abcdef	abcdefghi	abcdefghi	bcdef	abc	efghijkl	abcd	abcd	abcd	bcdefghi	abcdefg	abcdefghi	cdefghi
Prima	abcd	abc	abcdefg	abcdefg	abcdef	abcdef	abcdefghi	abcdefghi	abcde	ab	ghijkl	ab	abcd	abcd	ghi	abcdefg	abcdefg	bcdefghi
Stupicke S II	a	abc	ab	abcdefg	abcdef	abcdef	a	abc	ef	def	bcdefghi	bcdefgh	abcd	ab	bcdefghi	abc	efghi	hi
Cinquecento	abcd	abc	abcdef	abcdefg	abcdef	abcdef	abcd	abcde	f	abcde	efghijkl	abcdef	bcd	abcd	ghi	abcdefghi	bcdefghi	cdefghi
Montalegre	abc	a	abcdefg	abcdefg	abcdef	abcd	abcdefg	abcde	abcd	abcd	cdefghijk	abcdefg	abcd	a	fghi	abcdefg	abcdefghi	i
Caudar	a	ab	a	abc	bcdef	abcdef	ab	abcde	cdef	abcd	efghijkl	abcdef	abcd	abcd	defghi	abcdefghi	bcdefghi	ghi
Choigue	a	ab	abcdef	abcdefg	abcdef	abcde	abcde	abcdefg	abcd	abc	defghijkl	abcdefg	abcd	abc	hi	abcdefghi	abcdefg	bcdefghi
Naico	bcde	abcd	defg	abcdefg	abcdef	abcdef	cdefghi	abcdefghi	bcdef	abcd	hijkl	abcdefg	abcd	abcd	defghi	abcdefghi	abcde	fghi
Elbon Gator 17	abcde	ab	defg	bcdefg	abcde	a	bcdefghi	abcde	abcd	abcd	defghijkl	abcdef	abcd	ab	abcdefgh	a	abcd	bcdefghi
Wrens-5	abcde	ab	fg	bcdefg	abc	ab	abcdefghi	bcdefghi	abcde	a	abcdefgh	a	abcd	abcd	bcdefghi	abcd	abcdefg	bcdefghi
KWS Binntto	e	abcde	g	cdefg	f	abcdef	hi	defghi	bcdef	abcd	kl	bcdefghij	cd	abcd	abcdefghi	ab	abcdef	abcdefg

Variety	GW (g)		GN (pcs)		TGW (g)		HI (unitless)		SLW (g)		AB (g)		CI_F (Duaex units)		$\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (‰)		$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰)	
	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed	Control	Stressed
KWS Vinetto	cde	abcde	efg	bcdefg	def	abcdef	fghi	cdefghi	abcd	ab	ijkl	abcdefg	d	abcd	efghi	abcde	abc	abcdefg
SU Cossani	cde	abcde	fg	defg	bcdef	abcdef	ghi	efghi	abcd	abc	jkl	bcdefghij	bcd	abcd	bcdefghi	abcd	ab	abcdefg
SU Performer	de	abcde	g	abcdefg	abcdef	abcdef	i	cdefghi	abcd	abcd	l	cdefghij	bcd	abcd	abcdefghi	abcdefg	a	abcdefg
Conduct	abcde	ab	abcdefg	ab	ef	abcdef	abcdefghi	abcde	bcdef	abcd	ghijkl	abcde	bcd	abcd	hi	abcdefghi	abcdefg	defghi
Dukato	ab	abcd	abcd	abcde	bcdef	cdef	abcde	abcdef	bcdef	abcde	abcdefg	abcdefg	abcd	abcd	i	cdefghi	bcdefghi	efghi
Inspector	abcde	abc	abcdefg	abcdefg	ef	abcdef	bcdefghi	abcdefgh	abcd	abcd	ghijkl	abcdefg	abcd	abc	fghi	abcdefgh	abcdefg	bcdefghi
Matador	abcde	abcd	fg	abcdefg	abcdef	abcdef	bcdefghi	abcdefghi	bcdef	abcd	efghijkl	abc	abcd	abc	bcdefghi	abcdefg	abcdefg	abcdefghi
Dankowskie Amber	abcde	abcd	abcdefg	abcdefg	f	abcdef	bcdefghi	abcdef	bcdef	bcdef	fghijkl	abcdefg	abcd	abc	hi	abcdef	abc	bcdefghi
Dankowskie Rubin	abcde	abcd	abcdefg	abcdefg	ef	abcdef	abcdefghi	abcdefghi	bcdef	abcd	fghijkl	abcdefg	abcd	abcd	hi	abcdef	abcdefgh	bcdefghi

Supplementary Fig. S1 The course of mean daily air temperatures ($^{\circ}C$; measured at 2 m above ground level at 10-minute intervals using a Minikin T3 sensor, EMS Brno, Czech Republic) and mean daily global radiation ($W m^{-2}$; measured at the stand level at 1-minute interval using a Minikin RT Global Radiation Sensor, EMS Brno, Czech Republic) during the placement of experimental plants in the vegetation hall in Brno are presented. Precipitation (mm; Tripping Bucket Rain Gauge model 52202, R.M. Young Company, Traverse City, Michigan, USA) was measured in the nearby arboretum of Mendel University in Brno (approximately 450 m from the vegetation hall). The total precipitation recorded in the open area of the arboretum during plant cultivation was 170 mm. The total additional irrigation of plants per vegetation was 87 mm

Supplementary Fig. S2 a The course of mean daily air temperature (°C), mean daily relative air humidity (%), and mean daily photosynthetically active radiation ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) measured in the greenhouse of Photon Systems Instruments, Ltd., in Drásov at 1-minute intervals above the plant canopy using two Multisensor V130 probes (Photon Systems Instruments, Ltd., Drásov, Czech Republic). The placements of the probes in the greenhouse of Drásov with the phenotyping platform used in this study are shown in the right panel **b**. The mean values of the measured air temperatures, relative air humidity, and photosynthetically active radiation are calculated by central computer software to control the phenotyping platform and are stored directly as mean values instead of values of individual probes